

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MICROEMUL GEL CONTAINING *CODIAEUM VARIEGATUM* LEAVES EXTRACT AND ITS ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY

Ankita Tiwari¹, Kaushelendra Mishra^{2*}, Richa Verma³, Mehta Parulben D⁴,
Anupam Gautam⁵

¹Research Scholar- Lakshmi Narain College of Pharmacy, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh

²Professor- Lakshmi Narain College of Pharmacy, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh

³Associate Professor- Lakshmi Narain College of Pharmacy, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh

⁴Director- Lakshmi Narain College of Pharmacy, Kalchuri Nagar, Raisen Road, Bhopal,
Madhya Pradesh India-462021

⁵Assistant professor- Rajarshi Rananjay sinh College of pharmacy, Amethi UP
Corresponding author : Ankita Tiwari

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ABSTRACT

Present study focused on the formulation and evaluation of a microemulgel containing *Codiaeum variegatum* leaves extract and its antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*. Leaves of *Codiaeum variegatum* were collected and subjected to extraction using petroleum ether and ethanol, with ethanol yielding a higher extract percentage (6.37%). Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, glycosides, saponins, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds. The extract showed good solubility in ethanol and petroleum ether. A series of microemulsion formulations were developed, with formulation F5 showing optimal particle size (48.58 nm) and highest zeta potential (-30.2 mV), indicating good stability. This formulation was further incorporated into a gel base to form a microemulgel, which exhibited desirable physical properties including semi-solid consistency, yellowish colour, characteristic odour, pH of 5.9, high viscosity (5254±0.89 cps), and excellent spreadability (12.06 gm·cm/sec). The gel was non-irritating to the skin and remained stable under both normal and accelerated storage conditions for 90 days. The antifungal study demonstrated that the microemulsion gel had a concentration-dependent activity against *Candida albicans*, with the highest zone of inhibition (15 mm) observed at 1.5 mg/ml concentration, significantly outperforming the plain plant extract. These findings suggest that the formulated microemulgel of *Codiaeum variegatum* has promising potential as a topical antifungal agent.

Keywords: *Codiaeum variegatum*, microemul gel, antifungal activity, *Candida albicans*, phytochemical screening, particle size, zeta potential, topical formulation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In order for pharmacologically active compounds to exert their effects as efficiently as possible, they must be distributed and released into cells, tissues, and organs in a controlled manner. This is known as a "drug delivery system" (DDS) (Satoskar *et al.*, 2017). Unlike the traditional direct administration methods that rely on injections with needles. The distribution of numerous therapeutic substances has been greatly impacted by TDDS, particularly in the

treatment of disorders of the cardiovascular and central nervous systems, hormone therapy, and pain management (**Bala et al., 2014**).

Microemulsions are thermodynamically stable nano-micelles consisting of water, oil, surfactants, and co-surfactants, which are suitable for topical drug delivery to manage a variety of skin disorders such as acne (**Nguyen et al., 2024**). Microemulsions as drug delivery systems have proved to enhance the solubility of various poorly soluble actives and thus aided to enhance the bioavailability of the actives. Microemulsions not only aid to enhance the solubility of drug and thus its bioavailability but also aid to provide sustained therapeutic effect when formulated as microemulsion gels for topical use. Although microemulsions are well-known for their potentials to increase the permeation of drugs through the skin, most studies focus on the encapsulation and delivery of the pure drugs (**Kogan and Garti 2006**).

Codiaeum variegatum, like many members of the Euphorbiaceae family, produces a milky, caustic sap when cut or broken. This sap can cause irritation or harm if it contacts sensitive areas like the eyes, ears, mouth, or open wounds. While minor contact with skin usually causes no major issues, it may lead to mild burning, itching, or a rash, especially in individuals with sensitive skin. Pharmacological researches on the efficacy of croton plants showed that the extract of this plant have the following properties: abortifacient, antiamebic, antibacterial, anticancer, antifungal, and antioxidant (**Magwilu et al., 2022**). Other bioactivity test showed that the extract of the croton plant had antilithiatic activity. Bioassay against fish showed that at sub-lethal concentrations, this plant extract decreases haematological parameters and increased mortality (**Khan et al., 2024**). On *Culex* mosquito larvae, bioassay showed that *Cordiaem variegatum* extract has larvicidal properties. Phytochemical studies revealed that the plant leaf extract of croton contained glycosides, tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids, steroids, saponins, and triterpenoids (**Matara et al., 2021**).

This study shows the formulation and evaluation of microemul gel containing *Codiaeum variegatum* leaves extract and its antifungal activity

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Chemicals

Methyl paraben, Propylene glycol, Triethanolamine, Carbopol 934, Ethyl cellulose, HPMC, n-Octanol, DMSO, Methanol, DCM and Ethanol was procured from Merck. KBr was received from Sigma-Aldrich. Methanol was acquired from Rankem.

2.2 Collection of *Codiaeum variegatum* plant leaves

The *Codiaeum variegatum* plant's leaves were harvested and dried for three days in the shade at room temperature. To avoid contamination and deterioration, dried plant leaves were stored in sealed glass containers in a cold, dry atmosphere. A plant taxonomist confirmed the validity and purity of the therapeutic herb *Codiaeum variegatum* (**Mollick et al., 2011**).

2.3 Extraction Process of *Codiaeum variegatum*

The powdered *Codiaeum variegatum* leaves material (300) was subjected to a continuous hot percolation process using a Soxhlet apparatus (**Asrafuzzaman et al., 2024**).

The dried extract was weighed, and the percentage yield was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of extract}}{\text{Weight of Plant Material used}} \times 100$$

The dried extract was then held at low temperatures for more phytochemical examination and organoleptic characteristics (percentage yield, color, and smell).

2.4 Solubility study

The solubility of *Codiaeum variegatum* leaves powder in different solvents was qualitatively assessed based on the procedures outlined in the Indian Pharmacopoeia. A specific quantity of the powdered leaves was transferred into individual 10 mL test tubes, and 1 mL of various solvents—methanol, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), distilled water, chloroform, and acetone—was added to each tube. The samples were then examined to determine the extent to which the plant material dissolved in each solvent (Mfotie Njoya *et al.*, 2014).

2.5 Preliminary phytochemical investigations

To determine the existence of numerous beneficial chemicals, preliminary phytochemical investigations were conducted on *Codiaeum variegatum* leaves. The leaves extract was made using normal extraction methods, and established chemical tests were used for qualitative screening. The investigation's parameters included testing for alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, glycosides, phenols, terpenoids, and steroids. These phytoconstituents were detected via color changes or precipitate formation after certain reagent reactions. The results verified the existence of many pharmacologically important chemicals, hinting at the plant's potential for therapeutic applications (Njoya *et al.*, 2021).

2.6 Formulation of Micro-emulsion

To help to ascertain the extract solubility in various oils (oleic acid, Capryol 90, olive oil), surfactants (Cremophor RH 40, Tween 80), and co-surfactants (polyethylene glycol 400), an excess of medication was first added to 2 mL of chosen excipients in 5 mL stopper vials, followed by vortex mixing. Oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant were chosen based on how well they dissolved in the medication. With four components—olive oil as the oil phase, propylene glycol as a surfactant, and tween 80 as a co-surfactant, and distilled water as the aqueous phase—the micro-emulsion of the corresponding composition, as indicated in table 2, was created. For every batch, different surfactant to co-surfactant ratios was planned. The surfactant to co-surfactant ratio was selected, and a matching combination was prepared. Oil was added to the mixture making use of a magnetic stirrer, each liquid was thoroughly stirred until a homogeneous dispersion or solution was achieved. In these formulations, double-distilled water was employed to avoid the addition of surface-active contaminants (Yadav *et al.*, 2018, Singh and Vingkar 2008).

Table 1: Composition of micro emulsion formulation

Ingredients	FORMULATION CODE				
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i> (mg)	500	500	500	500	500
Propylene Glycol (ml)	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5
Tween 80 (ml)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Olive oil (ml)	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
Stirring Time (min.)	30	30	30	30	30
Distilled water	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5

2.7 Evaluation of prepared micro emulsion

2.7.1 Physical properties

Visual inspection was used to assess the micro emulsion's physical qualities, including appearance, transparency, and phase separation (Kumar *et al.*, 2020).

2.7.2 Particle size

Particle size is an important characteristic for characterizing micro emulsions. The micro emulsion's size was assessed with a Malvern Zeta sizer (Malvern Instruments).

2.7.3 Zeta potential

The zeta potential of the micro emulsions was measured using a Malvern Zeta-sizer (Malvern Instruments) (Kulkarni *et al.*, 2019).

2.7.4 Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM)

The morphological parameters of the Extract-loaded micro emulsion were investigated using an electron beam from a scanning electron microscope. A sputter coater was used to apply a thin layer (2-20 nm) of metal(s) such as gold, palladium, or platinum under vacuum. The pretreatment specimen was then bombarded by an electron beam, causing the creation of secondary electrons known as augers. Only electrons scattered at 90° were selected from the interaction between the electron beam and the specimen's atoms and processed further to obtain surface topography photographs using Rutherford and Kramer's Law (Gull *et al.*, 2020).

2.8 Formulation of micro-emulgel

Carbopol-934 was immersed in 50 mL of warm water (A) for 1.5 hr and was homogeneously dispersed using magnetic stirrer at 500 rpm. To create a stiff gel, 50 milliliters of warm water (B) was combined with carboxymethyl cellulose and methyl paraben in a different container and constantly agitated. Stirring continuously, mixtures A and B were combined. Following the addition of triethanolamine (dropwise) to balance the pH, the optimum formulation micro-emulsion was mixed into the dispersion to create the hydrogel. Propylene glycol, a permeability enhancer, was introduced at this point. The final dispersion was agitated until smooth gel was formed without lumps.

Table 2: Composition of micro-emulsion gel formulation

Name of Ingredient	Formulation I
Carbopol 940	1.0 gm
Carboxymethyl cellulose	1.0 gm
Propylene glycol	0.5 ml
Methyl paraben	0.05 ml
Micro-emulsion	5.0 ml
Triethanolamine	q.s
Water	100 ml

2.9 Characterization of extract loaded microemul gel formulation

2.9.1 Physical properties

The appearance was examined to ensure that the gel was clear, smooth, and devoid of noticeable flaws (Froelich *et al.*, 2017).

2.9.2 Measurement of pH

A digital pH meter was used to determine the pH (Daryab *et al.*, 2022).

2.9.3 Determination of Viscosity

The viscosity of microemulgel was tested using a Brookfield viscometer. (Hajjar *et al.*, 2018).

2.9.4 Skin irritation test

One Wistar rat was tested for skin irritation. One day before the trial, the rat's back skin was shaved for a 5 cm² area. After 24 hours, the rat was given optimal emulgel and tested for pain complaints. Scores were assigned based on observed symptoms of discomfort (Soliman *et al.*, 2010).

2.9.5 Spreadability test

Spreadability was tested using two 7.5 cm long glass slides. 350 mg of microemulgel was precisely weighed and applied to a single glass slide. Another glass slide was added 5 cm above it. A 5 gram weight was placed on the upper slide, and the diameter of the spread circle was measured in centimetres after one minute. The observed diameter indicates the gel's kind (Mishra *et al.*, 2016).

The time it took for the gel to travel a given distance from its starting point was measured. The following formula was used to determine the spread ability.

$$S = M \times L / T$$

Where, S-Spread ability, g.cm/s M-Weight put on the upper glass L-Length of glass slide T-Time for spreading gel in sec.

2.10 Antifungal activity of prepared microemul gel

2.10.1 Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) medium Preparation

To prepare 100 mL of Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) medium, 6.5 grams of the SDA powder were accurately weighed using a digital balance. The powder was slowly added to 100 mL of distilled water in a conical flask while stirring to ensure complete dissolution. The mixture was then heated gently on a hot plate with continuous stirring until the medium became clear, indicating that the components had fully dissolved. The flask was loosely covered with cotton plug and the medium was sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes at 15 psi. After sterilization, the medium was allowed to cool to around 45–50°C before being poured into sterile petri dishes under aseptic conditions. The plates were left undisturbed until the agar solidified and were then stored in a refrigerator at 2–8°C until further use (Kumar *et al.*, 2012).

2.10.2 Well Diffusion Assay

After the preparation of Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) medium plates Well Diffusion Assay was performed. A standardized suspension of *Candida albicans* was then evenly spread over the surface of the agar using a sterile cotton swab to ensure uniform growth. Wells of uniform diameter (6 mm) were aseptically punched into the agar using a sterile cork borer. Each well was filled with a specified volume (50–100 µL) of the microemulgel formulation. A positive control (placebo or blank gel) were also included in separate wells for comparison. The plates were incubated at 28–30°C for 24–48 hours. After incubation, the antifungal activity was assessed by measuring the diameter of the zone of inhibition around each well, indicating the extent of fungal growth inhibition by the formulation (Alwan, and Jaafar 2024).

2.11 Stability study

The stability of the microemulgel formulation was evaluated for three months at accelerated temperatures of 25 ± 2 °C and $60 \pm 5\%$ RH, and 40 ± 2 °C and $70 \pm 5\%$ RH. The formulation's physical properties, such as color, order, appearance, and particle size, were evaluated after 30, 45, 60, and 90 days. The formulation was tested for stability under accelerated storage settings for three months in accordance with the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) requirements. Color, odor, appearance, and particle size tests were utilized to assess for physical changes in the formulation. To comparison, all outcomes were contrasted with the final formulation at zero days (Abd-Allah *et al.*, 2010).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Plant Collection

Table 3: Plant collection

Plant name	Plant part used	Weight
<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i>	Leaves	300 gm

3.2 Percentage Yield

In phytochemical extraction, percentage yield is extremely essential since it allows you to calculate the standard extraction efficiency for a certain plant, different sections of the same plant, or different solvents.

Table 4: Percentage Yield of crude extracts of *Codiaeum variegatum* leaves extract

Plant name	Solvent	Color of extract	Theoretical weight	Yield (gm)	% yield
<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i>	Pet ether Ethanol	Brownish-yellow	300	7.34	2.44%
	Ethanol	Brown	292	18.62	6.37%

3.3 Solubility study

Table 5: Solubility study of *Codiaeum variegatum* leaves extract

Extract	Solvents	Observation/Inference
<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i>	Ethanol	Freely soluble
	Distilled water	Soluble
	DMSO	Soluble
	Chloroform	Sparingly soluble
	Petroleum ether	Freely soluble
	Acetone	Very slightly soluble

3.4 Preliminary Phytochemical study

Table 6: Phytochemical testing of *Codiaeum variegatum* leaves extract

Experiment	Presence or absence of phytochemical test	
	Pet. Ether extract	Ethanolic extract
Test for Carbohydrates		
Molisch's Test	Absent (-)	Present (+)
Benedict's test	Absent (-)	Present (+)
Fehling's Test	Absent (-)	Present (+)
Barfoed's Test	Present (+)	Present (+)
Iodine Test	Absent (-)	Present (+)
Glycoside		
Killer-Killiani test	Present (+)	Present (+)
Borntrager test	Present (+)	Present (+)
Tests for Alkaloids		
Dragendorff's Test	Present (+)	Present (+)
Mayer's Test	Present (+)	Present (+)
Wagner's Test	Absent (-)	Present (+)
Hager's Test	Present (+)	Present (+)

Test for Flavonoids		
Shinoda Test	Absent (-)	(+)
Test for Triterpenoids and Steroids		
Liebermann-Burchard Test for Triterpenoids and Steroids	Present (+)	Present (+)
Salkowski Test	Absent (-)	Present (+)
Tannin and Phenolic Compound Test		
Ferric Chloride Test	Present (+)	Present (+)
Gelatin Test	Present(+)	Present (+)
Lead Acetate Test	Present(+)	Present (+)
Test for Saponin		
Froth Test	Present (+)	Present (+)
Foam Test	Present (+)	Present (+)

3.5 Organoleptic properties

Table 7: The Organoleptic Studies of *Codiaeum variegatum* leaves extract

<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i>	Study
Colour	Brown
Odour	Distinctive
Appearance	Brownish Yellow

3.6 Evaluation parameter of micro emulsion

3.6.1 Visible observation of micro emulsion formulation

Table: 8 Visible observation of micro emulsion formulation

Formulation	Parameters	Observation
Micro emulsion	Colour	Yellowish
	Odour	Characteristic
	Appearance	Semi-solid

3.7 Particle size

Table 9: Particle size of micro emulsion

Formulation	Particle size (nm)	PI value %
Micro emulsion (F1)	67.66	27.4
Micro emulsion (F2)	89.70	25.6
Micro emulsion (F3)	141.94	25.9
Micro emulsion (F4)	139.82	23.2
Micro emulsion (F5)	48.58	31.2

Graph 6:- Graphical representation of Particle size of micro emulsion

The particle size analysis of the micro emulsion formulations showed sizes ranging from 48.58 nm to 141.94 nm, indicating successful formation of nano-sized emulsions. Among the formulations, F5 exhibited the smallest particle size (48.58 nm), which may contribute to better stability and skin penetration. The poly dispersity index (PI) values ranged from 23.2% to 31.2%, suggesting a moderately uniform size distribution across all formulations.

3.8 Zeta potential

Graph 7: Zeta potential (F1)

Graph 8: Zeta potential (F2)

Graph 9: Zeta potential (F3)

Graph 10: Zeta potential (F4)

Graph 11: Zeta potential (F5)

Table 10: Zeta potential of micro emulsion

Formulation	Zeta potential mV
Micro emulsion (F1)	-16.8mV
Micro emulsion (F2)	-12.5mV
Micro emulsion (F3)	-8.2mV
Micro emulsion (F4)	-9.6mV
Micro emulsion (F5)	-30.2mV

Graph 12: Graphical representation of Zeta potential of Micro emulsion

The zeta potential values of the micro emulsion formulations ranged from -8.2 mV to -30.2 mV, indicating varying degrees of stability. Formulation F5 showed the highest negative zeta potential (-30.2 mV), suggesting better electrostatic stability and lower risk of particle aggregation. In contrast, formulations F3 and F4 exhibited lower values, indicating relatively less stability.

3.9 Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM)

Figure 1: SEM (F5)

A scanning electron micrograph of the produced Micro emulsion at 2.00 kx magnification revealed that the Micro emulsion had smooth surface morphology and a sphere form.

3.10 Evaluation parameter of micro emulsion gel formulation

3.10.1 Physical properties

Table 11: Physical properties

Parameters	Results
Physical appearance	Semisolid gel
Colour	Yellowish Colour
Homogeneity	Absence of aggregates
Odour	Characteristic

The physical evaluation of the microemul gel formulation showed a semisolid gel consistency with a yellowish colour, Characteristic Odour and good homogeneity.

3.10.2 Determination of microemul gel formulation

Table 12: Measurement of pH, Viscosity, Skin irritation study and Spreadability test

Formulation	pH	Viscosity (cps)	Skin irritation study	Spreadability test (gm.cm/sec)
Microemul gel	5.9	5254±0.89	Not irritant observed	12.06

3.11 Results of anti-fungal activity of microemulgel F5 formulation

3.11.1 Anti-fungal activity of microemulgel

Table 13: Anti-fungal activity of microemulgel against *Candida albicans* fungus

Sample Name (mg/ml)	Zone of Inhibition (mm) of <i>Candida albicans</i>
Control (placebo or blank gel)	0 mm
Plant Extract (1mg/ml)	4 mm
microemulgel (1mg/ml)	7 mm
microemulgel (1.5mg/ml)	15mm

Figure 2: Anti-fungal activity of microemulsion gel against *Candida albicans* fungus

Graph 13:- Zone of inhibition of microemulsion gel against *Candida albicans* fungus

Table 14: Stability study of microemulgel

Time (Days)	25 ⁰ C±2 ⁰ C and 60 ± 5% RH				40 ⁰ C±2 ⁰ C and 70 ±5% RH			
	Colour	Odour	Appearance	Particle size nm	Colour	Odour	Appearance	Particle size nm
0	Yellowish	Characteristic	Semisolid gel	48.58	Yellowish	Characteristic	Semisolid gel	48.58
30	Yellowish	Characteristic	Semisolid gel	48.21	Yellowish	Characteristic	Semisolid gel	48.13
45	Yellowish	Characteristic	Semisolid gel	47.35	Yellowish	Characteristic	Semisolid gel	48.96
60	Yellowish	Characteristic	Semisolid gel	48.96	Yellowish	Characteristic	Semisolid gel	49.24
90	Yellowish	Characteristic	Semisolid gel	47.43	Yellowish	Characteristic	Semisolid gel	47.89

The stability study of the microemulgel (F5) formulation over 90 days showed consistent physical characteristics under both storage conditions (25 ± 2°C/60 ± 5% RH and 40 ± 2°C/70 ± 5% RH).

4. CONCLUSION

The microemulgel containing *Codiaeum variegatum* leaves extract was successfully formulated and evaluated for its physicochemical and antifungal properties. The ethanolic extract, rich in phytoconstituents, was effectively incorporated into a stable nano-sized microemulsion system. Formulation F5 emerged as the most effective due to its smallest particle size and highest zeta potential, contributing to greater stability and skin penetration. The final microemulgel formulation demonstrated favorable physical properties, stability, skin compatibility, and significant antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*, especially at

higher concentrations. These results support the potential of *Codiaeum variegatum*-based microemulgel as a promising candidate for topical antifungal therapy.

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